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D8 Draft best practice guide on relative primary radiation thermometry

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Best practice guide on relative primary thermometry using high temperature fixed points (HTFPs)

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ABSTRACT

This best practice guide provides comprehensive recommendations for the realization of thermodynamic temperature using relative primary radiometry at high temperatures. The document focuses on the application of high-temperature fixed points (HTFPs) based on metal-carbon eutectics as reference standards, enabling accurate and traceable temperature measurements above the silver point (1235 K). It outlines the theoretical background of relative primary thermometry, describes the required equipment - including furnaces, fixed-point cells, and radiation thermometers - and presents practical guidance on their preparation, operation, and optimization. Key aspects such as furnace temperature profiling, cell construction and filling techniques, inert atmosphere control, and measurement procedures are discussed in detail. The document also addresses the characterization and performance requirements of interpolation devices, including spectral responsivity, size-of-source effect, and detector linearity. Overall, the guide supports laboratories with limited primary radiometric capabilities by providing validated methodologies to achieve low-uncertainty temperature measurements and contribute to the realization of the SI Kelvin.

1 INTRODUCTION

The possibility to realize primary radiometric measurements remain restricted to a limited number of laboratories which has resulted in the development of "Relative" or indirect primary thermometry methods to meet the desire of laboratories with restricted capabilities to perform primary radiometric measurements. The alternative methods listed in this section represent an alternative to perform thermodynamic temperature by non-contact thermometry.

"Relative" or indirect primary thermometry is a measurement technique to measure thermodynamic temperature by using a known equation of state and anchoring measurements to one or more known temperatures that are realized by means of fixed points (FP).

- **Relative Primary Radiometry (High Temperatures):**

This method uses radiation thermometry (Planck's law) to determine thermodynamic temperature by anchoring measurements to recognized, highly reproducible, high-temperature fixed points (HTFPs). It is used above the freezing point of silver (≈ 1235 K) to provide a more accurate alternative to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90), which can suffer from large uncertainties at very high temperatures. The MeP-K recommends specific alloy-based HTFPs, such as Fe-C (≈ 1426 K), (Co-C (≈ 1597 K), Pd-C (≈ 1765 K), Pt-C (≈ 2011 K), Ru-C (≈ 2226 K), Re-C (≈ 2747 K) and WC-C (≈ 3021 K). The advantage of this method is that it provides comparable uncertainties to extrapolation based on ITS-90 and does not require the spectral responsivity measurement of the radiation thermometer.

- **Relationship to Defined Scales:**

The MeP-K allows these indirect primary methods to be used to determine the difference ($T - T_{90}$) between the thermodynamic temperature (T) and the ITS-90 scale temperature (T_{90}). This allows for the correction of existing scales and the gradual, direct implementation of the SI Kelvin without requiring an immediate, disruptive overhaul of industry standards.

- **Implementation and Updates**

The CCT (Consultative Committee for Thermometry) continuously updates the MeP-K to include new fixed points and improved measurement techniques, such as the addition of updated, lower-uncertainty values for metal-carbone high-temperature fixed points (e.g., in 2024 for Fe-C, Pd-C, Ru-C, and WC-C).

- **Possibilities to realize:**

- Extrapolation from any available HTFPs including Ag, Au or Cu
- Interpolation between available HTFPs

More details of these approaches can be found in [1].

2 EQUIPMENT

2.1 Furnace

Furnace generates required thermal environment to successfully realised melting and the freezing of the fixed points. Construction of the furnaces might be different, but goal is clear – to provide homogeneous and stable thermal environment alongside the fixed point crucible that would enable the melting/freezing plateaus of the installed cells.

2.1.1 Requirements

2.1.1.1 Ag/Au/Cu (ITS 90) fixed point

For realisation of ITS-90 cell, it is possible to find a commercial manufacturer on the market, who is able to provide complete set of the Fixed point(s) together with an appropriate furnace. Usually, these fixed points are much larger than established HTFPs, weight of the metal ingot is approximately 0.5 kg. Therefore, length of a plateaus can be several hours, then setpoints are optimised.

In case of small cells, with the same dimensions as agreed for eutectic HTFPs, these points are usually made by labs itself. Due to significantly less weight of the metal ingot inside the fixed point, duration of the plateau is usually only few minutes.

Note: Heat pipes are used for realisation of the ITS-90 big fixed point cells. They provide very uniform and stable environment, but similar environment can be generated also with the multiple-zone furnaces.

2.1.1.2 HTFP Fixed points

Actually, 7 HTFPs have actually assigned temperatures [2] covering temperature range from approx. 1150 °C to 2700 °C. Up to 1800 °C, HTFPs can be implemented in a common laboratory equipment represented by multizone furnaces. Special furnaces capable to generate temperatures higher than 1800 °C must be used to realise HTFPs Ru-C, Re-C and WC-C.

2.1.2 How to prepare furnace for FP realisation?

2.1.2.1 Cell holder and arrangement of the protective parts around the cell

The cell holder must be machined from high-purity graphite (> 99.99 %) and should cover as much of the cell surface as possible, except for the cavity opening. The purpose is to protect the cell from oxidation. A clearance must be maintained between the holder and the cell of at least 0.1 mm in diameter and 0.5 mm in length, in order to avoid mechanical stress during heating.

A set of diaphragms with increasing diameters must be installed in front of the cell to minimize the opening used for pyrometric observation, thereby limiting oxygen ingress into the furnace. However, these diaphragms must still have sufficient diameter to prevent vignetting caused by misalignment between the pyrometer and the furnace axis.

2.1.2.2 High temperature furnace

- HTBB 3200 pg or 3500 pg

The heating element of the HTBB 3200 pg or 3500 pg furnace consists of approximately fifty pyrolytic graphite rings compressed between two electrodes through which the electric current flows. The resistivity of the rings varies between 0.6 Ω/m and 2.5 Ω/m . It is therefore important to place the rings with the highest resistivity at the ends of the heating element to optimize the temperature profile along the cell [3]. It should also be noted that the temperature profile shifts toward the rear of the furnace as the temperature increases. Each fixed point thus has an optimal position near it. This position can be identified iteratively by measuring phase-change plateaus at a given position and then moving the cell within the furnace. The optimal position is the one for which the inflection point of the melting plateaus is maximal and the melting range is minimal [3].

- **Chino IR-R80:**

The heating element of the Chino IR-R80 furnace consists of a hexagonal-shaped coil made of molded carbon fabric. It is arranged around a carbon tube into which the cell is inserted. Unlike the HTBB furnace, the temperature profile cannot be adjusted. The optimal position of the cell is specified by the manufacturer. However, optimization tests can still be performed by moving the cell by ± 1 cm around this position.

- **Thermogauge:**

The heating element of the Thermogauge furnace is a graphite cylinder, which serves also as a cavity, where fixed point or measurement by comparison is realized. At the both cylinder ends it is placed into a copper electrodes, which are used to heat up the system through high currents flowing through the graphite element. Furnace have to be cooled by the water and in order to prevent graphite parts also presence of the argon is needed. Temperature profile of the furnace cannot be adjusted, but it is possible to find optimal position for the best HTFP cell performance by positioning cell slightly around the cavity.

- **Multi purpose“ furnace:**

Another type of furnace where high temperature fixed points (HTFPs) can be realized is the so-called “multi-purpose” furnace. This category typically includes single-zone (or alternatively 3 or more zone) furnaces that have openings on both sides. These can be used, for example, for thermocouple (TC) calibration or, after inserting a blackbody cavity, for pyrometer calibration via the comparison method. The temperature range of these furnaces is usually from approximately 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 1600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (although in practice, they are more commonly utilized from 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ upwards). This means they allow for the realization of FPs ranging from Ag to Pd-C. Usually, these furnaces contain an internal work tube made of aluminum oxide, Al_2O_3 (alumina), with typical dimensions of around 600 mm to 1100 mm in length and 40 mm to 70 mm in diameter.

For single-zone furnaces, the temperature field uniformity is inferior compared to multi-zone or heat-pipe furnaces. To achieve the required temperature field uniformity (and potentially stability), it is necessary to appropriately select insulation materials, such as ceramic or mineral wool plugs, which are placed inside the tube behind the FP. On the front side of the

FP, various sets of rings (made of graphite or alumina) are used to improve uniformity as well as to ensure an inert atmosphere.

When using a furnace with an alumina (or similar material) work tube, thermal expansion must be taken into account. Due to thermal expansion, alumina can elongate by up to 9 mm per 1000 mm of length. Consequently, the entire tube, along with the cell holder, shifts linearly toward the free end as the temperature rises. As a result, the geometric center of the furnace (and thus the position of the fixed point relative to the pyrometer) shifts realistically by several millimeters. This displacement must be factored in during the precise alignment of the pyrometer's optical axis. In addition to this tube deformation, a phenomenon known as tube sagging in the center can occur, particularly when the tube is supported only at both ends. This is the primary reason why continuous verification of the pyrometer alignment with the FP target aperture is absolutely essential.

2.2 Fixed points

2.2.1 Construction

2.2.1.1 Selection of a graphite parts (crucibles, CC sheets, protection parts)

The parts used for cell fabrication must be made of high-purity graphite, especially those in contact with the metal. In general, the densest graphites provide the best properties for cell manufacturing: small grain size, low porosity, high mechanical resistance, and high thermal expansion coefficients. Therefore, graphite with a density higher than 1.80 g/cm^3 should be used. The purity should be higher than higher than 5N (10 ppm of impurity).

Unlike pure metals, metal–carbon alloys migrate and solidify on the surface of the graphite components forming the cell. During temperature cycles between room temperature and the melting temperature, the differential expansion between the alloy and the crucible generates mechanical stresses that can cause cell failure. To overcome this problem, laboratories now build cells by adding a rigid cylinder centered inside the cell using flexible graphite foils. This sacrificial cylinder, kept slightly free between the graphite foils, protects the crucible while also improving the temperature profile along the ingot. This typical configuration (Figure 1), known as the “hybrid design”, was developed at LNE-CNAM about twenty years ago and has since undergone many improvements [4].

Figure 1: Cross section of a “hybrid design” crucible used for high-temperature fixed point. The rigid inner cylinder is kept slightly free between the C/C sheet. It absorbs mechanical stresses and contributes to the protection of the external parts.

2.2.1.2 Purity and the shape of the metal

Cell filling is performed by preparing the metal–carbon mixture in advance using materials with the highest possible purity, ideally higher than 4N5 for the metal and higher than 5N for the graphite. The shape of the metal is not critical; it may be supplied as (1–2) mm cubes or cylinders, powder, shots or any other shape provided the metal can fall into the space between the cavity and the cylinder. Metal powders are easier to mix with graphite powder, but their lower bulk density before melting requires several successive filling operations.

2.2.1.3 Eutectic composition of HTFPs

Metal–carbon phase diagrams provide the graphite proportion corresponding to the eutectic or peritectic transition of high-temperature fixed points (HTFPs). However, this proportion should be reduced because the surrounding graphite parts in contact with the metal also contribute carbon to the mixture during the first melt. It is therefore preferable to prepare the mixture with a lower graphite content than that indicated by the phase diagrams. Table 1 shows suitable proportions for the most commonly used fixed points. These proportions are indicative and can be adjusted following the ingot surface at the completion of the first filling. The greater the amount of graphite visible at the surface, the more the graphite proportion should be reduced during the second filling.

Table 1: Graphite proportion that must be mixed with the metal for the filling preparation. The density of the M-C ingot is about 10 % less than the density of the pure metal.

Metal-Carbon	Fe-C	Co-C	Pd-C	Pt-C	Ru-C	Re-C	WC-C
Phase transition (°C)	1153	1324	1492	1738	1953	2474	2748
density of pure metal (g/cm ³)	7.9	8.9	12	21.4	12.2	20.8	19.3
Transition (Eutectic/Peritectic)	E	E	E	E	E	E	P
Eutectic composition in phase diagrams (% mass)	4.3	2.6	2.7	1.2	2	1.3	6.1
Graphite proportion suggested in M-C the mixture preparation (% mass)	3.2	2	1.7	0.3	1	0.5	4.5

2.2.1.4 Positioning the cell during the filling and measurement

The filling operations are carried out with the cell in the vertical position. The furnace temperature must be highest at the bottom of the crucible so that melting starts from the

bottom of the cell. The furnace temperature should not exceed the melting temperature of the M–C mixture by more than 30 °C. Otherwise, the crucible supplies additional carbon to the ingot, resulting in a carbon concentration higher than the eutectic (or peritectic) composition, which weakens the cell. This excess carbon then migrates toward the surface of the ingot during solidification.

Measurements are performed with the cell in the horizontal position. The cell must be placed in a temperature profile that is as uniform as possible.

2.2.1.5 Cell construction

2.2.1.5.1 Step-by-step filling

The cell assembly first consists of wrapping the C/C sheets inside the crucible. The sleeve is then inserted. The M-C mixture is prepared in a glove box with a graphite proportion generally 1% below the eutectic composition. Target mass of the M-C compound is prepared.

The part of the prepared mixture is then poured into a crucible, until crucible is visibly filled and installed into a furnace. First melting is applied, and after cooling down the cell, another portion of the M-C mixture is poured into a crucible. The furnace setpoint is chosen to be only about 30 °C above the melting temperature in order to prevent the mixture from becoming saturated with excess carbon from the graphite components.

Each filling step, less material is put into a crucible due to an increasing volume of the ingot in a cell. Full filling of the cell may take from the 8 to 15 steps, based on the type of the material used for filling.

2.2.1.5.2 Piston method

The cell assembly first consists of wrapping the C/C sheets inside the crucible. The sleeve is then inserted, and the extension is screwed onto the top of the crucible (Fig. 2a). The M–C mixture is prepared in a glove box with a graphite proportion generally 1% below the eutectic composition. A mass 5 % to 10 % greater than the target mass is prepared to compensate for the additional volume created by erosion of the graphite sleeve.

The mixture is then poured into the extension, either completely when the metal is in the form of cubes or shots, or only half-filled in the case of powders. In the latter case, the first melting cycle is performed without the disk and piston. In the first case (or in the second case after a first cycle), the disk is positioned on top of the mixture and the crucible is placed in the furnace (Fig. 2b). The piston and rod are then installed, and the cell is heated. The furnace setpoint is chosen to be only about 30 °C above the melting temperature in order to prevent the mixture from becoming saturated with excess carbon from the graphite components.

Once the phase transition is complete, pressure is applied to the rod until the piston comes to rest on the extension. In this position, the ring covers the top of the cell. The excess mixture flows through the small opening at the center of the rod and piston (Fig. 2c). A cooling rate lower than 1500 °C/min, especially for materials with high thermal expansion such as Fe–C, Co–C, Pd–C, and Ru–C, is then applied. After cooling, the extension is cut at the base of the sample (Fig. 2d). Two disks made of C/C sheet are inserted into the cap, which is then screwed onto the crucible.

2.2.2 Characterisation

To get a good reading from the fixed-point cell, at the correct temperature, optimisation of the furnace, and the cells position therein, is required. This includes positioning the cell correctly in the furnace in relation to temperature gradients and setting the optimal furnace setpoints and ramp speed.

The temperature profile of the furnace, in the region of interest where the cell will be placed, is an important factor for a successful realisation of a high temperature fixed point. There are several ways of measuring the temperature profile. One straight forward method is by placing an appropriate thermocouple in the furnace and moving it in steps across the region of interest, giving it some time to stabilise at each point. A disadvantage of this method is that the temperature range is limited and that the thermocouple in each point will measure over a larger area due to heat conduction. Another way is by using a small (graphite) black body cavity in the furnace. The blackbody should be short to limit the area over where the temperature is measured. This blackbody then needs to be moved across the region of interest while the temperature is measured with a pyrometer. It is also possible to create one graphite block with several cavities, with different depth, thereby avoiding having to move it while the furnace is hot, although the pyrometer will then have to be moved between the different cavity positions. All these methods have their advantages and limitations, and the temperatures measured are often only an approximation of the actual profile in the furnace. The temperature profile should be measured at the temperatures where the furnace will be used as it can change in shape, and especially in amplitude, for different temperatures.

Care must be taken when moving things inside a hot furnace as fast temperature changes can damage parts of the furnace. For example, inserting a room temperature rod or thermocouple into a hot ceramic tube can easily crack the tube.

Figure 2: Filling procedure: (a) preparation of the cell, (b) before melting, (c) after melting and application of pressure on the piston, (d) filled cell with cap.

The fixed-point cell should be placed in a position in the furnace that has as small of a temperature gradient as possible as a larger gradient makes the melting plateau less well defined and the temperature harder to identify. It is possible to somewhat reduce the gradients in the furnace by placing insulation in front and behind the cell. Graphite felt or solid graphite rings works well for this. Another way finding a good position in the furnace is by trial and error; by moving the cell in steps across the region of interest, acquiring at least one plateau at each position and then comparing the length and shape of the curves. A disadvantage with this method is that it can take a lot of time and the temperatures where it is possible are limited.

Once the optimal furnace position has been found it is possible to further optimize the plateau by adjusting the setpoints and ramp speed of the furnace. A setpoint of (10 to 20) °C above and below the melting point can be an appropriate starting point. Increasing the setpoint makes the plateau shorter but can make it more well defined. The ramp speed is

sometimes limited by the furnace and can vary from a couple of °C/min to 20 °C/min or more. Increasing the ramp speed can give a more well-defined plateau.

If the plateau is unusually short, not very well defined or at the wrong temperature, even though it is in the right place in the furnace and the setpoints and ramp speed were chosen appropriately, it is possible that there is something wrong with the cell. Impurities in the metal most often lowers the melting temperature and makes the plateau less well defined. Large voids or damage to the cell can also affect the melting plateau negatively.

2.2.3 Realisation

2.2.3.1 How to protect the fixed point

Main protection is created by the inert atmosphere (usually high purity argon). Argon flow can be guided to the furnace in different ways, e.g. directly to the cell area; entering the front/back side of the furnace or is purged from both ends of the tube. This depends on the furnace construction and have to be solved by laboratory.

In order to reduce oxidation atmosphere around the fixed point, additional graphite or ceramic parts can be inserted into the furnace around the HTFPs. Parts, placed in front of the HTFPs cell, are very often used also to create an optical path. In certain types of furnaces, especially in case when the diameter of the tube furnace is bigger than the diameter of the cell, cell can be closed in a protection “container”, which has two functions. It positions cell in the middle of the furnace tube together with the protection function.

2.2.3.2 How to set appropriate argon flow?

The most commonly used material for fixed-point (FP) cells and cell holders inside furnaces is high-purity graphite. A graphite begins to oxidize (degrade) at temperatures above approximately 450 °C therefore, it is necessary to maintain an inert atmosphere within the furnace where the FP cell is positioned. Argon (Ar 99.99 % [5]) is most frequently utilized as the inert gas. Commercial manufacturers of double-open-ended furnaces (which typically feature an alumina work tube extending through the entire length of the furnace) offer specialized accessories to ensure an inert atmosphere, though this usually requires a certain minimum tube length. These accessories commonly include the capability to evacuate the internal volume of the alumina tube and subsequently backfill it with the inert gas. When employing these types of furnaces for FP realization, one side of the tube must remain open to provide an unobstructed optical path for the pyrometer.

Consequently, one of the most effective methods for maintaining an inert atmosphere in the center of the tube's working volume—assuming the rear side behind the FP cell is insulated, for example, with mineral wool—is the implementation of a thin alumina capillary tube (with a diameter of 2 mm or 3 mm). This capillary is inserted from the viewing side (the side from which the pyrometer aims into the furnace) and placed so that it does not obstruct the pyrometer's optical path (e.g., along the bottom of the main furnace work tube), with its inner exit positioned close to the FP cell.

From experience of different NMIs, a nominal inert gas flow rate of approximately 6 L/min is recommended, although some sources cite lower values. This can serve as an initial

baseline value, which can subsequently be increased or decreased depending on the observed degree of degradation (oxidation) of the graphite components inside the furnace. It is vital to note that the FP cell itself is the most critical component in the furnace; thus, if the oxidation is confined to the sacrificial graphite shielding components at a reasonable rate, the setup can be considered optimal. If the inert atmosphere protection provided by a single thin tube proves insufficient, a second capillary tube can be introduced from the rear side of the FP cell. For the initial testing of the inert atmosphere efficacy, it is best to proceed without the actual FP cell by using sacrificial graphite test rings instead. Only after verifying the suitability of the inert atmosphere should the FP cell be installed in the furnace. Furthermore, if the internal volume of the furnace is evacuated prior to FP realization and then backfilled with inert gas, a rapid gas filling rate (high flow surge) may physically displace the FP cell from its position inside the furnace.

2.2.3.3 Melting and freezing slopes

Differential stresses between the ingot and the crucible are maximal at temperatures close to ambient and minimal at temperatures near the phase transition. For this reason, it is advisable to avoid any thermal shock, particularly around ambient temperature where stresses are highest. Heating and cooling rates depend on the robustness of the cells. It is generally recommended not to exceed a heating rate of 1500 °C/h and a cooling rate of 700 °C/h. However, small-cell sizes (cavity length less than (20 to 25) mm) or cells of specific designs (removable cavity) can withstand higher rates. The cells used for this project can support heating and cooling rate of 3000 °C/h. However, it is recommended not to remove the cell from the furnace at temperatures above 100 °C.

2.2.3.4 Melting temperature

Temperature setpoints must be chosen so that they are always higher than the temperature profile along the cell. Early cells were operated with setpoints of about ± 25 °C around the plateaus because temperature profiles were not fully controlled at the time. Nowadays, the temperature gradient along the cells is on the order of 3 °C to 5 °C for a properly positioned cell in the furnace. Setpoints can therefore be reduced to ± 10 °C or ± 15 °C, although they may still be maintained at ± 25 °C depending on the desired plateau duration or for reproducibility tests.

After heating up from ambient temperature, it is recommended to wait about 15 minutes for the furnace to stabilise. This stabilisation temperature is generally between 30 °C and 10 °C below the melting temperature of the fixed point. The first melting is then initiated by a temperature step of about +10 °C to +30 °C above the plateau, using the fastest possible ramp in order to limit furnace temperature variations during plateau observation. The control pyrometer should not act abruptly on the power supplied during the observation of the plateaus.

2.2.3.5 Freezing temperature

The freezing plateau is not used as a reference as its reproducibility is not as good as that of the inflexion point of the melting plateau.

When the ingot is in the liquid phase, the freezing setpoint can be adjusted to a temperature between 10 °C to 30 °C below the freezing temperature. Supercooling depends on the thermal conditions and the impurities in the metal. It is generally between 1 °C to 3 °C below the freezing temperature, but in some cases it can reach 250 °C to 280 °C for Re-C and the WC-C fixed points. In such cases, the ingot remains in the liquid phase despite its temperature is far below the freezing temperature. Freezing may begin after waiting approximately 5 to 10 minutes, but if not, the furnace temperature must be lowered by up to 300 °C to induce freezing. The plateau then becomes visible but only for a very short duration. Once it is finished, the setpoint must be readjusted from 10 °C to 30 °C below the phase transition and the furnace must be allowed to stabilised for 15 minutes. In certain cases, deep supercooling may be mitigated by directly switching the melting setpoint to the freezing setpoint immediately after the end of the melting plateau, without waiting for the furnace stabilisation.

2.2.3.6 Furnace effect

The furnace thermal environment has been identified as a significant source of uncertainty in the realization of HTFPs. The furnace temperature profile can affect measurements in several ways: through the high reflectivity of the fixed-point cavity at glancing incidence angles, which increases the contribution of reflected furnace radiation to the radiometer signal; through apparent variations in wall emissivity along the cavity; and, in extreme cases, by inducing non-ideal motion of the solid–liquid interface, which may migrate from front to back or back to front rather than advancing radially along the cavity axis. A particularly important and somewhat counter-intuitive observation is that when the thermal gradient shifts from cooler to hotter toward the front of the cell, the melting curve may appear to improve qualitatively, while quantitative analysis shows this improvement to be illusory. In practice, optimal realization requires positioning the HTFP blackbody within the most thermally uniform region of the furnace. The axial temperature distribution can be assessed either by scanning the furnace wall radiance temperature with a radiation thermometer through the side aperture or by using a dummy cell with a cavity-like geometry and translating it along the furnace axis after thermal equilibrium is reached. When these conditions are satisfied, plateau realizations consistently yield high point-of-inflection temperatures, values close to the true point-of-inflection and liquidus temperatures, and narrow melting ranges. Depending on the fixed-point material and the care taken in the setup, the resulting furnace-effect standard uncertainties range from (25 to 75) mK under best conditions to (30 to 150) mK under typical laboratory conditions [6].

The thermal inertia of the furnace during setpoint changes also plays a key role in furnace effect. Among the three high-temperature furnaces most commonly used in laboratories - Thermogauge, Chino IR-R80, and HTBB 3200pg- the first two respond more quickly to a change in setpoint than the HTBB 3200pg, because the smaller mass of their heating elements.

The PID (proportional, integral, derivative) control system also plays an important role in the furnace effect. In Figure 3, the furnace response to a setpoint change (red curve) generates a furnace response (green curve) that may be either fast or slow, depending on the chosen PID parameters.

Figure 3: The furnace response (green curve) to a change of setpoint (red curve) is linked to the regulation system and has an effect to the position of the inflexion point.

This response influences the position of the inflection point and therefore the temperature assigned to that point. A fast response produces a sharp entry into the plateau and shifts the inflection point toward the middle of the plateau, whereas a slow response results in a rounded entry into the plateau, with the inflection point shifting toward two-thirds of the plateau. The temperature difference is directly linked to the melting range, approximately from 10 % to 20 % of its value.

2.3 Interpolation device (Radiation thermometer)

Relative Primary Radiometry at high temperatures is one of the recommendations of the MeP-F for the realization of the radiation temperature scale above approximately 1200 K. The method is based on the physical laws of radiation thermometry, namely Planck's law and its approximation using the Planck version of the Sakuma–Hattori equation. Thermodynamic temperature is determined by anchoring measurements to the currently established and officially recognized highly reproducible HTFPs by the BIPM-CCT, together with their reference phase-transition temperatures and associated uncertainties. At present, seven HTFPs and the Cu point are available, with reference temperatures distributed almost uniformly between 1200 K and 3000 K. Relative Primary Radiometry enables the calibration of a radiation thermometer at these reference points, followed by interpolation between them to determine temperatures across the range. This approach has been successfully applied by many NMIs over the last several decades in the medium-temperature range, from the indium (In) point to the copper (Cu) point, approximately from 150 °C to 1100 °C. The experience gained from this practice can also be applied to the high-temperature range. In particular, because the realization principle is based on interpolation between calibrated reference points, the relative nature of the measurements relaxes some of the strict requirements imposed on instruments used in absolute radiometry for radiation thermometry. In Relative Primary Radiometry, the instrument is calibrated at several reference points and the results are interpolated; therefore, the instrument is referred to as an “interpolation device” [7]. This concept allows partial simplification of the instrument design with respect to stringent metrological requirements, reducing cost and increasing the possibility of implementation in many NMIs while still maintaining low uncertainty in the realization of the temperature scale. Below is a brief recommendation on the minimum capabilities required for the interpolation device.

2.3.1 Requirements

2.3.1.1 Spot Size

As described in Section 2.2 (Fixed Points) and consistent with common practice in the field, the aperture size of modern HTFP cavities is typically standardized at around 3 mm, considering tolerance in cell size, compatibility across different high-temperature furnaces, and cost aspects. To properly match these cells, the interpolation device should have a target spot size of less than 1 mm at the defined target distance. This small spot size, together with the reduction of vignetting effects including SSE effects, allows easier alignment of the device in front of the furnace for both calibration and measurement purposes.

2.3.1.2 Viewing Angle:

The target distance, i.e. the distance between the cell aperture inside the blackbody furnace and the “nose” of the interpolation device (generally defined by the entrance aperture stop of the device), determines the viewing angle of the interpolation device. A target distance in the range of 700 mm to 850 mm is commonly used for most radiometers and interpolation devices. This distance should be optimized to achieve a good balance with the furnace geometry, particularly the separation between the furnace entrance and the position of the

cell inside the furnace. Positioning the interpolation device as far as practical from the furnace also helps maintain better thermal stability of the instrument during measurements, especially at higher temperatures.

2.3.1.3 Viewing Conditions

Along the optical path from the cavity aperture inside the furnace to the objective lens (i.e. the aperture stop) of the device, all diaphragms, stops, and other apertures (including those commonly used inside the furnace to improve temperature uniformity along the cell length) should have diameters larger than the viewing cone defined by the interpolation device in order to minimize vignetting effects. This balance between a small viewing angle and the overall system design must be carefully maintained. Minimizing the viewing angle of the device must be well balanced against its physical size. A compact device design is also essential for transportability and ease of use, particularly during installation on an optical table using translation stages—preferably motorized—for accurate alignment with the cavity aperture, including precise tilt and pitch adjustment and positioning. The diameter of each aperture along the optical path should be calculated based on its position within the solid viewing angle of the device. In particular, each aperture diameter should be at least 20% larger than the instantaneous spot size of the beam at the corresponding position, ensuring that no clipping occurs throughout the entire optical path.

2.3.1.4 Device Optical Design

It is considered best practice to minimize the number of optical components (and optical surfaces) along the radiometric path inside the device in order to minimize effects related to light scattering, diffraction, and reflection. All of these effects contribute to the device SSE. The optical train should include only the essential elements, typically an objective lens, aperture stops, field stops, a Lyot stop, a collimating lens, a beamsplitter or a movable mirror (used for the visual channel to support alignment of the device with the HTFP cell inside the furnace or with the aperture of a blackbody by the operator), an interference filter, and a detector coupled with a transimpedance amplifier.

The optical design should be optimized for a small viewing angle (i.e. the effective magnification of the system along the radiometric channel) and balanced against the overall system size, with the primary objective of minimizing SSE.

A common minimal approach in optical system design is as follows: the optical layout of an interpolation device consists of an aperture stop (correlated with the size of the objective lens) and a diameter-limited achromatic objective lens, which focuses the incoming radiation onto a field stop. This configuration implies a system magnification defined at the field stop plane and determines the required field stop diameter, which should correspond to a target spot size of less than or approximately 1 mm.

A subsequent second lens (with a diameter of one inch or less) collimates the light and images the aperture stop onto the Lyot stop. The positioning of the Lyot stop at this plane is essential, as it determines the capability of the device to suppress stray radiation and thus minimize SSE. For more detailed specifications of the Lyot stop, the work by [8] should be consulted. Along with the proper optical layout of the system, the positioning of the Lyot stop

is of significant importance for interpolation devices. Further along the optical path, an interference filter and a silicon photodiode, coupled with a transimpedance amplifier, are used for signal conversion.

All mechanical diaphragms should be manufactured from materials with low thermal expansion and mounted in a temperature-stabilized block (at least for the Lyot stop, the interference filter, and the detector system). The internal walls and mechanical parts should be blackened using appropriate methods, such as chemical treatment or coating with high-absorption black paint exhibiting extremely low reflectance.

2.3.1.5 System components

The objective lens should be an achromatic lens with a clear aperture ranging from 40 mm to a maximum of 60 mm in diameter, equipped with an anti-reflection coating optimized for the spectral range of approximately 650 nm to 950 nm. The quality of this lens plays a significant role in the device SSE; therefore, a surface quality of 40–20 scratch-dig is considered a common minimum requirement for the lens specification.

For high-temperature radiation thermometry, interference filters are generally recommended due to their narrow bandwidths and the availability of filters with different combinations of central wavelength and bandwidth from commercial manufacturers. These two parameters are among the main factors determining the performance and operating range of the interpolation device. Interference filters with central wavelengths from approximately 550 nm to 950 nm are commonly used. The bandwidth, typically defined as the FWHM, generally ranges from 10 nm to 50 nm depending on the intended application. According to Planck's law, shorter wavelengths provide higher temperature sensitivity but lower signal levels; therefore, shorter central wavelengths are preferred for higher-temperature measurements, while longer wavelengths are more suitable for lower-temperature applications. Wider bandwidths increase detector signal and improve the signal-to-noise ratio, but may increase saturation effects and reduce spectral selectivity and accuracy. Narrower bandwidths improve spectral selectivity and precision but require higher detector sensitivity. For interpolation devices operating from approximately 1000 K to 2000 K, longer central wavelengths with relatively wider bandwidths are generally suitable, whereas higher-temperature applications require shorter central wavelengths and narrower bandwidths.

For the temperature range from approximately 1000 K up to 3000 K, a silicon (Si) detector is preferred. Although multi-element detectors can also be used, a single detector with a clear aperture larger than 5 mm is desirable, while a 10 mm diameter detector is preferable, particularly in terms of linearity.

To significantly reduce dark noise and improve short-term stability and overall measurement reproducibility, a cooled detector is preferred. Alternatively, the detector may be maintained at a controlled temperature, for example around (28 to 30) °C, to ensure stable operating conditions during all measurements. Commercial transimpedance amplifiers with selectable gain settings can be used. At minimum, three gain settings of 10^6 , 10^7 , and 10^8 V·A⁻¹ should be available for measurements across the 1200 K to 3000 K range.

2.3.1.6 Characterisation

2.3.1.6.1 *Wavelength (relative spectral responsivity)*

In relative-radiometry-based radiation thermometry, highly accurate relative measurements of the interpolation device are generally required when only one or two HTFPs are available for scale realization. If at least three HTFPs are available and can be realized within the laboratory, the radiation temperature scale may be established directly using the Planck-form Sakuma–Hattori equation, thereby reducing the dependence on detailed prior knowledge of the spectral responsivity of the radiometer. In contrast, when only a single HTFP is available, the effective wavelength and spectral bandwidth of the radiometer become critical parameters in the temperature calculation. Under such conditions, accurate characterization of the spectral responsivity of the interpolation device is essential.

The measurement of relative spectral responsivity of the interpolation device should generally follow procedures similar to those used for realization of ITS-90 above the silver point, as described in relevant WG5 guidance documents and CCT recommendations. Spectral responsivity measurements should preferably be performed using a monochromator-based system with a double-monochromator configuration in order to minimize stray-light and out-of-band transmission effects. Double-grating monochromators equipped with gratings blazed within the wavelength range from approximately 600 nm to 900 nm are generally recommended for radiation thermometry applications operating in the visible and near-infrared spectral regions.

For high-accuracy measurements, modulation techniques are strongly recommended. In such systems, monochromatic radiation is modulated by a mechanical chopper, while the detector signal is processed using a lock-in amplifier synchronized to the chopping frequency. This approach improves the signal-to-noise ratio and enables more reliable determination of weak out-of-band spectral transmittance components that may otherwise introduce systematic errors into the determination of effective wavelength and bandwidth parameters.

The wavelength scan should cover not only the principal responsivity band of the thermometer but also adjacent spectral regions where residual out-of-band transmission may occur. Within the main responsivity band, a wavelength increment of approximately 0.1 nm is recommended for accurate determination of the peak wavelength and bandwidth characteristics. Additional scans over wider spectral regions are recommended for identification of stray-light effects. Appropriate bandpass filters should also be used to suppress second- and higher-order diffraction contributions. Contributions to the uncertainty arising from monochromator wavelength calibration, spectral bandwidth effects, polarization sensitivity, higher diffraction orders, and out-of-band transmission should be carefully evaluated and included in the uncertainty budget, as described in the WG5 documents.

For applications where realization of ITS-90 is also intended, the spectral responsivity measurements of the radiation thermometer under test and the calibration measurements of the reference detector should be performed over the same wavelength range and using identical wavelength intervals. The reference detector is typically calibrated in absolute

responsivity units (A/W) and traceable to a cryogenic radiometer through silicon trap detectors or equivalent primary radiometric standards.

Two parameters should be retrieved from the spectral responsivity measurements, namely the central wavelength λ_c and the bandwidth (σ^2) at half of the maximum responsivity (FWHM), as illustrated in the Figure 4.

Figure 4: Parameters to be retrieved from the spectral responsivity measurement of the radiation thermometer [9].

2.3.1.6.2 Size-of-source effect (SSE)

SSE, being one of the most important characteristics of an interpolation device and significantly affecting its performance, requires accurate metrological characterization. Two methods, namely the “direct method” and the “indirect method,” are the most widely used approaches in this field. The direct method is well suited for pyrometers with relatively large spot sizes of approximately 6 mm and operating at low temperatures below about 150 °C. The indirect method, on the other hand, is more suitable for radiation thermometers with small spot sizes around 1 mm and provides the best results at temperatures above 150 °C. In relative radiometry-based radiation thermometry, the indirect method is considered the de facto standard approach.

For the assessment of the SSE of an interpolation device, a setup comprising a large integrating sphere with a diameter of approximately 400 mm or greater is typically required. The sphere should include an output port with a diameter of at least 60 mm (aperture of most furnaces used in the HTPFs realisations). Commonly, the sphere contains four incandescent lamps connected in series. To minimize specular reflections at the sphere output port, four internal baffles should be positioned at appropriate locations inside the sphere. The lamps are supplied with controlled DC current and are switched on at least one hour prior to measurements in order to establish quasi-isothermal operating conditions.

A set of apertures with different diameters, typically ranging from 2 mm, including 3 mm and 5 mm, up to 50 mm, should be available in order to simulate variable-diameter radiance sources. In addition, a glass window containing a black spot of approximately 3 mm diameter positioned precisely at the center of the window should be used. The black spot must coincide with the center of the integrating sphere output port. Another identical blank glass window without the black spot, manufactured from the same glass material, should also be available in order to eliminate the influence of the window transmittance during SSE measurements.

During the measurements, a selected aperture together with the black-spot window is mounted in front of the sphere output port. The interpolation device is aligned to the center of the black spot and adjusted to obtain the minimum signal level. Measurements are then performed over a sufficient time interval to acquire an adequate number of signal samples for averaging and standard deviation analysis. Subsequently, the black-spot window is replaced by the blank glass window in order to record the background signal while eliminating the transmittance contribution of the supporting glass substrate. The transmittance of the black spot within the operating wavelength range of the interpolation device should be as low as possible, typically below 0.01%.

This procedure is repeated for all aperture diameters. It is generally considered good practice to begin measurements with the smallest aperture diameter, proceed toward larger diameters, and then repeat the measurements again in decreasing diameter order. Typically, at least three complete measurement sets are required for statistical analysis. At each measurement step, the dark signal of the interpolation device should also be acquired by closing the entrance aperture of the device with a suitable cap.

The SSE can be calculated using the following expression:

$$SSE (\%) = \frac{S_{spot} - S_{dark}}{S_{aperture} - S_{dark}} \quad (1)$$

where (S_{dark}) is the dark signal of the device, (S_{spot}) is the signal measured when the thermometer is focused on the black spot, and ($S_{aperture}$) is the signal measured when the selected aperture is combined with the blank glass window. The measurement is repeated for all apertures with different internal diameters.

After completion of the measurements, the SSE characteristic of the device is typically presented as an SSE plot, as illustrated in the Figure 5.

Figure 5: Example of the SSE plot of the device

2.3.1.6.3 Linearity

Linearity of a radiometer is defined as the degree to which its output signal is directly proportional to the incident radiant power over its operating range. In the temperature range from 1000 K up to 3000 K, the assignment of spectral radiance or radiance temperatures of blackbody sources relies on ratios of detector signals that may differ by several decades. To perform such ratio measurements with low uncertainty, the linearity of the detectors used in interpolation devices must therefore be carefully characterized.

Among several available techniques, the “superposition method” and the “dual-aperture method” are the two most widely used methods in radiometry and pyrometry. A detailed comparison of these methods within the scope of pyrometric applications was reported in [10].

For temperatures from the Cu-point up to approximately 1900 K, a flux-doubling method employing two highly stable lamps (lamp-based radiance method) can be used (Figure 6). The setup consists of two lamps, each powered by a separate stabilized power supply controlled through feedback from the pyrometer or detector under test. Apertures and shutters are positioned in front of each lamp.

Figure 6: Setup for linearity characterisation

During the measurements at a given radiance temperature, the signal of the device is first recorded using only the first lamp while the second lamp is blocked by its shutter, yielding the signal (S_A). Subsequently, the first lamp is blocked and the second lamp is opened, resulting in the signal (S_B). Finally, both shutters are opened simultaneously and the combined signal (S_{AB}) is measured.

For higher temperatures, typically above 2000 °C, the dual-aperture method is commonly employed. This method is based on the use of two independent apertures (or optical paths) that illuminate the detector either individually (S_A and S_B) or simultaneously (S_{AB}). For an ideally linear detector, the response obtained when both apertures are open simultaneously is equal to the sum of the responses measured from each aperture separately.

The detector non-linearity coefficient can be expressed as:

$$NL = \frac{S_{AB} - S_{dark}}{S_A + S_B - 2S_{dark}} \quad (2)$$

The non-linearity correction factors were calculated by first normalizing the correction at the lowest (S_{AB}) signal level. Intermediate correction factors can be derived by linear interpolation between the two nearest points surrounding a given signal level. This procedure produces a continuous correction function ($NL(S)$), which can then be applied to measured signals to compensate for cumulative detector non-linearity effects.

It is worth noting that, for interpolation devices calibrated using several HTFPs, particularly one near the lower end and another near the upper end of the temperature range, the influence of detector non-linearity becomes significantly reduced. This is because the scale realization is based on interpolation principles over a comparatively limited signal range.

In contrast, this is not the case for ITS-90 realization, where the detector signal is measured at the lower end of the temperature range at relatively low radiance levels, typically at one

of the Ag, Au, or Cu fixed points, and subsequently extrapolated to much higher radiance temperatures. Under such conditions, detector non-linearity becomes one of the dominant sources of uncertainty.

3 CONCLUSION

This guide summarizes current best practices for implementing relative primary radiation thermometry using high-temperature fixed points. It demonstrates that reliable and accurate thermodynamic temperature measurements can be achieved through careful control of the entire measurement system, including furnace design and operation, fixed-point cell construction, and the performance of the radiation thermometer used as an interpolation device.

The results highlight the importance of optimizing furnace temperature profiles, ensuring proper positioning of fixed-point cells, and maintaining a stable inert atmosphere to minimize oxidation and measurement uncertainties. The construction and filling of HTFP cells, including material purity and design considerations, are shown to play a critical role in achieving reproducible phase-transition plateaus. Furthermore, the characterization of the radiation thermometer—particularly in terms of spectral responsivity, size-of-source effect, and detector linearity—is essential to ensure accurate interpolation between fixed points.

Relative primary radiometry provides a practical and accessible approach for many laboratories to realize the thermodynamic temperature scale with uncertainties comparable to those obtained using ITS-90 extrapolation methods, while offering a pathway toward direct SI traceability. Continued improvements in fixed-point data, furnace technology, and instrument characterization will further enhance the robustness and accuracy of this method. The procedures and recommendations presented in this guide contribute to the harmonization of practices across laboratories and support the broader implementation of high-temperature primary thermometry.

4 REFERENCES

- [1] *Mise en pratique for the definition of the kelvin (MeP-K) Annex 2*, Bureau International des Poids et Mesures, Sèvres, France, 2019.
- [2] *MeP-K for primary high-temperature scale realisation: Relative primary thermometry (radiometry)*, Version 7.0, final revision 21 May 2024, Bureau International des Poids et Mesures, Sèvres, France.
- [3] F. Bourson, S. Briaudeau, B. Rougié, and M. Sadli "Determination of the furnace effect of two high-temperature furnaces on metal-carbon eutectic points" AIP Conf. Proc. 1552, 380 (2013) doi: 10.1063/1.4821389
- [4] F. Bourson, S. Briaudeau, B. Rougié, M.Sadli "Development around the Co-C eutectic point at LNE-INM/Cnam" Acta Metrological Sinica Vol. 29, 4A10 Presented at Tempbeijing Oct. 2008
- [5] Howard W. Yoon, David W. Allen, Charles E. Gibson, Maritoni Litorja, Robert D. Saunders, Steven W. Brown, George P. Eppeldauer, and Keith R. Lykke, "Thermodynamic-temperature determinations of the Ag and Au freezing temperatures using a detector-based radiation thermometer" Appl. Opt. 46, 2870-2880 (2007)
- [6] D. Lowe; F. Bourson; M. Florio; F. Girard; G. Machin; J. Mantilla; M. J. Martin; H. Nasibli; O. Pehlivan; M. Sadli, "High-temperature fixed-point furnace uncertainties" AIP Conf. Proc. 3230, 070006 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0234816>
- [7] D. Lowe "A pyrometer for calibration traceable to a future thermodynamic temperature scale" Meas. Sci. Technol. 24 015901, 2013
- [8] Yoon, H.W.; Allen, D.W.; Saunders, R.D. *Methods to reduce the size-of-source effect in radiometers*. Metrologia, 42, 89–96, 2005.
- [9] Ertürk, M.; Karabulut, M.; Kadi, Ö.F.; Gözönünde, C.; Broberg, P.; Olsen, Å.A.F.; Nasibli, H. MultiFixRadSoft: A Comprehensive Tool for Primary Relative Radiometric Scale Realization in Radiation Thermometry, Sensors, 26, 2489, 2026.
- [10] Yoon, H.W.; Butler, J.J.; Larason, T.C.; Eppeldauer, G.P. *Linearity of InGaAs photodiodes*. Metrologia, 40, S154–S158, 2003